

4th ISAJ India-Japan symposium on Emerging Materials, 11 Oct., 2013, Tokyo, Japan.

ISAJ
INDIAN SCIENTISTS ASSOCIATION IN JAPAN

4th India-Japan Symposium

India-Japan Symposium on Emerging Materials for Health, Environment and Safety

October 11, 2013

Indian Embassy Auditorium, Tokyo

Organized by

Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ)

Supported by

Embassy of India

ISAJ
INDIAN SCIENTISTS ASSOCIATION IN JAPAN

Honorary Patron:

H.E. Ms. Deepa Gopalan Wadhwa
The Ambassador of India

Honorary Advisor:

Dr. Chadaram Sivaji
S & T Counsellor, Embassy of India

Convener:

Dr. Alok Singh

Co-convener:

Dr. Baiju G. Nair

Organizing Committee:

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Dr. Kedar Mahapatra
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Mr Mahendra Kumar Pal
Mr Shanthanu R. Menon
Dr. Manoj Eradath
Dr. Kanaka Raju Pandiri

PROGRAM

8:00-9:00 Registration

Session 1: Inaugural Session

Time		Speaker
9:00	Lighting of the Lamp	
9:05	Welcome address	Sunil Kaul , Chairman, ISAJ
9:10	Introduction	Alok Singh , Convener
9:15	Inaugural address	Her Excellency Ms. Deepa Gopalan Wadhwa , The Ambassador of India
9:25	Address	C. Sivaji , Counselor, Science & Technology, Embassy of India
9:40	Keynote address: “RIKEN's new 5-year basic plan and collaboration with Indian Institutions”	Kenji Oeda , Executive Director, RIKEN
10:10	Special lecture: International Students in Japan: Current scenario, challenges and prospects	Neelam Ramaiah , University of Tokyo
10:20	Vote of thanks	Baiju Nair , Co-convener

10:25 – 11:00 Group photo and coffee break

Session 2: Materials for Health Chair: Dr. Manish Biyani (Univ. of Tokyo)

Time	Speaker	Topic
11:00	Yoshihiro Ito , RIKEN	Bio-orthogonal and combinatorial design of functional proteins
11:20	Biju V Pillai , AIST, Takamatsu	Engineered nanomaterials: Potential agents for biological applications or potentiators of toxicity
11:40	Madoka Takai , Univ. of Tokyo	Effect of Nanoscale Phase-Separated Surface of Amphiphatic Block Copolymer on Cellular Adhesion Behaviors
12:00	Hiroshi Abe , Hokkaido Univ.	Nano-structured RNA for RNA interference
12:20	Tahei Tahara , RIKEN, Wako	My Personal History with India
12:40	Ran Gao, (P11) AIST, Tsukuba	Involvement of MicroRNAs in human cancer cells senescence
12:45	Archana Kumari, (P16), Osaka Univ.	Regulation of epidermal cell proliferation under stress conditions
12:50	Manjiri R. Kulkarni, (P21) Tokyo Univ. Agri. & Tech.	Molecular insights into the residue responsible for stereotype specificity...

12:55- 14:00 Lunch and Poster Session

14:00	K. VijayRaghavan	Special address via web by Secretary, Department of Biotechnology, Government of India
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Session 3: Materials for environment Chair: Masanobu Naito (NIMS)

Time	Speaker	Topic
14:15	Takuya Nakashima , Nara Inst. of Sci. & Tech.	Toward Highly Efficient Molecular Switch
14:35	Hideki Abe , National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS)	Intermetallic Pt ₃ Ti nanoparticles: CO-poisoning tolerant electrocatalyst for the polymer-membrane electrolyte fuel cells
14:55	C. Subramaniam , TASC/AIST, Tsukuba	Remarkable current-carrying-capacity of carbon nanotube-copper composite
15:15	Teruhiko Matsubara , Keio University	Design of peptide drug against influenza: selection of hemagglutinin-binding peptides from random peptide libraries
15:35	Jatish Kumar, (P5), NAIST, Nara	Self assembly and circularly polarized luminescence of chiral bichromophoric...
15:40	Rajesh Kodiyath, (P23), NIMS	Highly active and stable intermetallic Pt ₃ Ta nanostructure for the methanol...
15:45	Yosuke Shirai, (P32), NIMS	Catalytic activity of acid- and/or alkali-treated Ni ₃ (Al,V) atomized powder

15:50 – 16:10 Coffee break

Session 4: Materials for energy and safety Chair: Hideki Abe (NIMS)

Time	Speaker	Topic
16:10	Daisuke Fujita , NIMS	Graphene and h-BN Formed by Surface Segregation and Precipitation
16:30	Toshiji Mukai , Kobe Univ.	Grain refinement of magnesium alloys for improving mechanical performance
16:50	Asima Sultana , AIST	Mitigation of vehicular pollutants for clean environment
17:10	Arockiakumar R., (P2), NIMS	High temperature shape memory behavior of Ti-Pd-Zr-Hf alloy
17:15	Debabrata Payra, (P8), NIMS	Synthesis and studies of novel multi-functional polymer coating for...
17:20	Baozhen Jiang, (P26) NIMS	Effect of sever plastic deformation in the precipitation behavior of ... Ti5553 alloy
17:25	Yoshiaki Tanaka, (P28) U. Tokyo	TEM/STEM observation of kink- deformed microstructures in LPSO-Mg

Session 5: Panel Discussion

	The role of Indian scientists in Japan in bridging the Science & Technology between India and Japan
17:30-18:15	Moderated by: Sanjeev Sinha (Sun and Sand Advisors)
	C. Sivaji, Neelam Ramaiah, Daisuke Fujita, Tahei Tahara, Sunil Kaul.

18:15 – 18:30: **Closing & Awards**

डा. आर. चिदम्बरम्

भारत सरकार के प्रमुख वैज्ञानिक सलाहकार
एवम्

अध्यक्ष, मॉडर्न साइंस को वैज्ञानिक सलाहकार समिति
(पूर्व अध्यक्ष, परमाणु ऊर्जा आयोग)

Dr. R. Chidambaram

Principal Scientific Adviser to the Govt. of India
&

Chairman, Scientific Advisory Committee to the Cabinet
(Former Chairman, Atomic Energy Commission)

सत्यमेव जयते

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Message

The theme of the 4th India-Japan Symposium on October 11, 2013, by ISAJ, viz. Emerging Materials for Health, Environment and Safety” is important and appropriate. The borders between disciplines are fuzzy today, particularly among chemistry, crystallography, condensed matter physics and materials science. Because of the great improvement in computing power and the advances in knowledge of condensed matter, computational design of new materials with desirable properties can also now be attempted. I remember visiting the National Institute of Materials Science (NIMS), Tsukuba, some years back and being told that “nanotechnology-driven materials science for sustainability” is the guiding concept when selecting research areas in NIMS and that their focus is on promotion of advanced materials research for social needs. The Indian perspective on materials science also includes what I have called “directed basic research” (apart from applied research), i.e. directed to areas where technology foresight analysis indicates possibility of global leadership by India.

*India values greatly its scientific cooperation with Japan and I am very happy that ISAJ is promoting this cooperation *inter alia* by holding these symposia. I also would like to congratulate ISAJ for growing from strength to strength since its inauguration in January 2009, where it was my pleasure and privilege to be present.*

I wish the Symposium all success.

R. Chidambaram

(R. Chidambaram)

6th October, 2013

Dr. Sunil Kaul

Chairman, Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ)

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ISAJ

INDIAN SCIENTISTS ASSOCIATION IN JAPAN

भारत का राजदूत

MESSAGE

I am very happy to learn that the 4th Symposium of Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ) is being organised at the Indian Embassy auditorium on October 11, 2013.

The subject of the symposium is extremely pertinent for the benefit and welfare of our people since it focusses on emerging materials for health, environment and safety. While thanking the members of the ISAJ and the participants in the symposium, I would encourage them to continue the good work that they are doing to enhance Indo-Japan collaboration in the field of science and technology.

I wish ISAJ success in all its endeavours.

(Deepa Gopalan Wadhwa)

Tokyo

October 4, 2013

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独立行政法人 物質・材料研究機構
National Institute for Materials Science

Sukekatsu Ushioda
President
National Institute for Materials Science
Tsukuba, Japan

Congratulatory Message

As President of National Institute for Materials Science (NIMS), I would like to congratulate the Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ) for its successful contributions to the collaborative scientific activities between India and Japan. It is my great pleasure to see that ISAJ is organizing its 4th India-Japan Symposium this year. I especially note the importance of the theme "Emerging materials for health, environment and safety." Our institute is engaged in frontier research in all kinds of advanced materials for the welfare of the society.

I note that a large number of presentations in this symposium will be from NIMS, many of them by Indian researchers. A number of Indian researchers in Japan are engaged in materials research, a large number (42) of who work at NIMS. I believe that some of that work will be presented at this symposium.

I wish all success to the organizers of this symposium and congratulate ISAJ for its successful contributions to the collaborative scientific activities between India and Japan. I hope our relation will deepen in all areas that involve us both.

Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ)

Chairman's Welcome

I, on behalf of ISAJ, extend warm welcome to all the delegates to India-Japan Symposium on Emerging Materials for Health, Environment and Safety, the 4th annual symposium of ISAJ, a registered Non-Profit Organization (NPO) in Japan.

Our association was born out of a need of a rapidly growing community of Indian researchers in Japan to interact with each other. It acts as the main body of the Indian researchers in Japan. Among its various activities, it maintains a website for giving information and through which we can be contacted, and it runs a mailing list for information exchange. At the moment there are over 230 members on the mailing list.

ISAJ was formally inaugurated by Dr. R. Chidambaram, Principal Scientific Adviser to Government of India in the science city of Tsukuba on January 2009. Steadily expanding since then, ISAJ has its functional chapters from Hokkaido to Kyushu in Japan – some very active and some not so active because of the short term of its members in Japan – and has been continuously making sincere efforts to scale up its potential in networking scientists from India and Japan.

ISAJ has been holding regular meetings including scientific presentations and networking in different chapters such as Tsukuba and Tokyo. Annual symposium is one of its major activities, which brings together a number of Indian researchers and their colleagues, who showcase their research done in Japan. This is our fourth annual symposium today.

The symposium this year is focused on very timely issues including emerging materials for health, environment and safety. We believe that this interdisciplinary meet will generate a platform for new discoveries and innovation. Besides keynote talks and plenary lectures by eminent leaders in the field, there will be poster presentations by young researchers.

The Embassy of India has been the main supporter of ISAJ from its conception and progress. We sincerely appreciate the initiative of the then Indian Ambassador Shri Hemant Krishan Singh and S&T Counsellor Dr. Pankajakshan Thadathil in structuring and growth of the ISAJ. We feel privileged that Her Excellency Ms Deepa Gopalan Wadhwa, Ambassador of India, and S&T Counsellor, Dr. Chadaram Sivaji has been actively encouraging in continuing ISAJ activities.

I sincerely hope that your active participation will make this symposium an enjoyable meet and further enhance our S&T relations and friendship.

With best regards,

Sunil Kaul
Chairman
ISAJ

Conveners' Welcome

On behalf of the organizing committee we welcome you to the 4th India-Japan symposium of the Indian Scientists Association in Japan (ISAJ). This year's main theme is "Emerging materials for health, environment and safety."

Materials are markers for human progress. New materials enable new technologies. Major milestones in human evolution have been stone, bronze, iron, steel and, more recently, silicon ages. Today we have a variety of advanced materials, be it nano-bio technology with huge benefits for health care, materials which make technological progress sustainable with respect to the environment, or the traditional metals and alloys which form the backbone of our society for making buildings, transport and power plants, but with much higher performance and reliability today and with much less impact on the environment. These topics will be talked about in today's symposium, in about 14 lectures by experts who have gathered from many parts of Japan. Besides these, there will be 10 short oral presentations by young researchers on their posters. Research by young researchers in all fields of science and technology are showcased in about 34 poster presentations. As can be seen from the research work presented in the symposium, materials are a truly interdisciplinary subject, combining diverse fields such as biology, mineralogy, chemistry, physics, materials science and mathematics. We hope that the specialists from these diverse fields gathered here today will have a fruitful and enjoyable time talking and discussing with each other.

The symposium would not have been possible without the generous support of the Embassy of India, especially Dr. Chadaram Sivaji. Counselor, Science & Technology. We gratefully acknowledge the kind sponsorship from the Bank of India, New India Assurance Company, the State Bank of India and Komiya Yoko Memorial Association.

Finally, we take this opportunity to thank everyone for overwhelming support. We sincerely hope that we all will enjoy the symposium and that it will inspire India-Japan collaborations and friendships along with developing stronger ties in Science and Technology.

With best regards,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Alok Singh'.

Alok Singh
Symposium Convener

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Baiju G. Nair'.

Baiju G. Nair
Symposium Co-convener

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Special	Neelam Ramaiah	Tokyo Univ.	<i>International Students in Japan: Current scenario, challenges and prospects</i>
Plenary	Yoshihiro Ito	RIKEN, Wako	<i>Bioorthogonal and combinatorial design of functional proteins</i>
Plenary	Vasudevanpillai Biju	AIST Takamatsu	<i>Engineered nanomaterials: Potential agents for biological applications or potentiators of toxicity</i>
Plenary	Madoka Takai	Univ. of Tokyo	<i>Effect of nanoscale phase-separated surface of amphiphilic block copolymer on cellular adhesion behaviors</i>
Plenary	Hiroshi Abe	Hokkaido University	<i>Nano-structured RNA for RNA interference</i>
Plenary	Tahei Tahara	RIKEN Wako	<i>My personal history with India</i>
Plenary	Takuya Nakashima	NAIST, Nara	<i>Toward Highly Efficient Molecular Switch</i>
Plenary	Hideki Abe	NIMS	<i>Intermetallic Pt₃Ti nanoparticles: CO-poisoning tolerant electrocatalyst for the polymer-membrane electrolyte fuel cells</i>
Plenary	C. Subramaniam	AIST Tsukuba	<i>Remarkable current-carrying-capacity of carbon nanotube-copper composite</i>
Plenary	Teruhiko Matsubara	Keio University	<i>Design of peptide drug against influenza: Selection of hemagglutinin-binding peptides from random peptide libraries</i>
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Plenary	Toshiji Mukai	Kobe University	<i>Grain refinement of magnesium alloys for improving mechanical performance</i>
Plenary	Asima Sultana	AIST Tsukuba	<i>Mitigation of vehicular pollutants for clean environment</i>

Posters

- P1** **Daisuke Kageyama** National Institute of Agrobiological Sciences
Sex manipulation by microbes- Are you male or female?
- P2** **R. Arockiakumar** National Institute for Materials Science
High temperature shape memory behavior of Ti-50Pd-2.5Hf-2.5Zr alloy
- P3** **Aniruddha Adhikari** RIKEN, Wako
Elucidating the water structure at nonionic lipid/ water interfaces using novel interface selective nonlinear spectroscopy
- P4** **Julian Mark Rosalie** National Institute for Materials Science
Effect of precipitation strengthening on slip and twinning in a Mg-Zn alloy
- P5** **Jatish Kumar** NAIST, Nara
Self-assembly and circularly polarized luminescence of chiral bichromophoric perylene bisimides
- P6** **Shiva Kumar Singh** National Institute for Materials Science
Synthesis of $K_8-Al_x-Si_{46-x}$ new thermoelectric clathrate compound
- P8** **Debabrata Payra** National Institute for Materials Science
Synthesis and studies of novel multi-functional polymer coatings for metals and alloys
- P9** **Ankit Singla** Chiba University
Biochar influencing methane flux in paddy ecosystem
- P10** **Chuang Huang** AIST Tsukuba
Effect of withaferin A and methoxy-withaferin A in human cancer cells: Bioinformatics and biochemical insights
- P11** **Ran Gao** AIST Tsukuba
Involvement of MicroRNAs in human cancer cells senescence
- P12** **Ye Liu** AIST Tsukuba
Anti-apoptotic proteins Bcl-2 and Bcl-xL interact with mortalin in cancer cells resulting in p53 activation
- P13** **Mijung Kim** AIST Tsukuba
CARF overexpression-mediated growth arrest of cancer cells involve p53 protein
- P14** **Yue Yu** AIST Tsukuba
Role of hnRNP-k in cancer metastasis
- P15** **Jihoon Ryu** AIST Tsukuba
Non-mitochondrial mortalin promotes human tumorigenesis through activation of telomerase and hnRNP-K
- P16** **Archana Kumari** Osaka University
Regulation of epidermal cell proliferation under stress conditions
- P17** **Pratheep Kumar S.** NIMS
Flame retardancy of Vermiculite composite coatings on wood

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Keynote Address

RIKEN'S NEW 5-YEAR BASIC PLAN AND COLLABORATION WITH INDIAN INSTITUTIONS

Kenji Oeda

Executive Director, RIKEN (Institute of Physical and Chemical Research), Wako, Saitama

This year is the first year of RIKEN's new 5-year basic plan. In order to promote science, technology, and innovation, we have set up the following five pillars of our mission:

1) To promote strategic, prioritized research and development based on national and social needs, 2) To provide, use and share state-of-the-art infrastructure, 3) To effectively promote creative and challenging advanced interdisciplinary research that will bring about a paradigm shift, 4) To effectively return the results of research to society for application in industry, medicine and other areas by establishing partnerships and networks within and outside RIKEN, and 5) To establish an open, vibrant research environment that will train and promote outstanding researchers.

Our new organization will focus on making optimum use of our comprehensive strengths to bring research to a whole new level in the areas of developmental biology, brain science, quantitative biology, bioresources, computational science, synchrotron radiation, and accelerator-based science.

In the area of green innovation, we are working on emergent materials for new energy sources and conservation measures, photonics research for novel and precise applications for light, and sustainable resources directed at developing technologies for recycling and energy.

In the area of life innovation, we are pursuing integrated medical science research to contribute to the development of medical treatment and preventive medicine. Immunology, genomics, structural biology, molecular imaging science and omics are RIKEN's areas of strength. We are planning to integrate these areas of science to establish a leading-edge interdisciplinary research environment.

Today international collaboration is indispensable for outstanding science. This year RIKEN has established a new organization, the Global Research Cluster, for the purpose of strengthening collaboration with other institutions. In my presentation I will focus on our recent progress in collaboration with Indian institutions. Our strategy for collaboration with industry will also be presented.

Special Lecture

INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS IN JAPAN: CURRENT SCENARIO, CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS

Neelam Ramaiah

Office for International Cooperation & Exchange, Graduate School of Agricultural & Life Sciences, The University of Tokyo, 7-3-1 Hongo Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo, Japan

I pursued research in Marine Biologist until 2003 when I was entrusted the responsibility of managing our graduate school's Office for International Cooperation & Exchange (OICE). Our school annually hosts nearly 250 international students from diverse cultural and educational backgrounds. A quarter, or more, of the international students joining our graduate school are unable to speak Japanese when they first arrive in Japan. Even if one knows the language, the numerous initial formalities at various offices can be very challenging for a newcomer.

My office is an interface between the international community and the university. Creating a comfortable and conducive environment for the international students through bilingual support, advising on daily life/ research related matters, dilemmas, troubles etc., as well as overall management of the international office are my major responsibilities. In my presentation, I will share the insights obtained from working in this field over the past 10 years, the current scenario and matters related to international students, with reference to the Indian students in Japan.

Plenary 1

BIOORTHOGONAL AND COMBINATORIAL DESIGN OF FUNCTIONAL PROTEINS

Yoshihiro Ito

Chief Scientist and Director of Nano Medical Engineering Laboratory, RIKEN

Visiting Professor of Tokyo Metropolitan University, Tokyo Institute of Technology and Hokkaido University

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Recently the protein engineering has been extended into bioorthogonal protein engineering by development of specific chemical or enzymatic modification technology. On the other hand, combinatorial approach, which is called molecular evolutionary engineering or in vitro selection) has also provided a new design tool for functional peptides. By these methodologies various designs of new proteinous materials have been possible for biological/medical applications. Here the progress of new molecular design of proteins will be discussed from the standpoint of preparation of binding growth factors of which importance increased in the research filed of biomaterials.

Plenary 2

ENGINEERED NANOMATERIALS: POTENTIAL AGENTS FOR BIOLOGICAL APPLICATIONS OR POTENTIATORS OF TOXICITY

Vasudevanpillai Biju

Health Research Institute, AIST, 2217-14 Hayashi-Cho, Takamatsu, Kagawa 761-0395 and PRESTO, Japan Science and Technology Agency

Recent research trends at an interface among chemistry, materials science, biology and medicine show focusing effects on the *in vitro* and *in vivo* applications of nanomaterials towards multiplexed detection and sensing, multimodal bioimaging, gene and drug delivery, and cancer chemotherapy and phototherapy. The size-dependent tunable electronic state of materials, which is unlocked in the past two decades, is the most exciting innovation that underlies the present status of nanoscience and nanotechnology [1]. As a result of this innovation, engineered nanomaterials have not only infiltrated

into various disciplines of basic research but also reformed our lives as key elements of electronic displays, nanomedicine, bioimaging probes, cosmetics, and food [2]. One of the most exciting aspects of our ongoing research is the ever accelerating progress of engineered nanomaterials towards practical applications in bioimaging [3-5] and photodynamic and photothermal therapy of cancers [6,7]. Among various nanomaterials, semiconductor quantum dots and metal quantum clusters are of particular interest owing to their exceptionally bright and highly stable photoluminescence in the UV-Vis-NIR spectral range. We mostly focus on improvement of the photoluminescence properties of quantum dots and quantum clusters and subsequent formulation these nanomaterials for intracellular delivery and *in vivo* imaging. Conversion of nanomaterials into their bioconjugates is a prerequisite for labeling of biomolecules, cells and tissues. The biomolecules recruited to the surface of nanomaterials depends on a particular application aimed for, such as single-molecule detection, extracellular labeling, gene delivery, intracellular delivery, or *in vivo* imaging. Cells can be labeled using bioconjugated nanomaterials in a nonspecific or targeted manner. Targeted labeling of cells using nanomaterials conjugated with antibodies, proteins, peptides, amino acids, liposomes, aptamers, DNA, RNA, or certain simple biomolecules has been extensively investigated in the recent past, which bridges between nanomaterials and biomedical imaging [2]. In addition to the specific labeling of certain proteins in selected cell lines, we also highlight on MRI and fluorescence imaging by the intracellular and *in vivo* delivery of bioconjugated quantum dots and quantum clusters. Nonetheless, the stimulation of oxidative stress and the release of heavy metal ions by photoactivated chalcogenide quantum dots result in the cell death *via* the damage of vital biomolecules, summary of which is also sketched in this presentation.

- [1] V. Biju, T. Itoh, M. Ishikawa, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2010**, 39, 3031.
- [2] P. Jones, S. Sugino, S. Yamamura, F. Lacy, V. Biju, *Nanoscale* **2013**, 10.1039/C3NR03118G.
- [3] A. Anas, T. Okuda, N. Kawashima, T. Itoh, M. Ishikawa, V. Biju, *ACS Nano* **2009**, 3, 2419.
- [4] V. Biju, A. Anas, H. Akita, T. Itoh, H. Harashima, M. Ishikawa, *ACS Nano* **2012**, 6, 3776.
- [5] E. S. Shibu, S. Sugino, K. Ono, H. Saito, A. Nishioka, S. Yamamura, M. Sawada, Y. Nosaka, V. Biju, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2013**, DOI: 10.1002/anie.201304264.
- [6] E. S. Shibu, M. Hamada, N. Murase, V. Biju, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. C.* **2013**, 15, 53.
- [7] V. Biju, S. Mundayoor, R. V. Omkumar, A. Anas, M. Ishikawa, *Biotechnol. Adv.* **2010**, 28, 199.

Plenary 3

EFFECT OF NANOSCALE PHASE-SEPARATED SURFACE OF AMPHIPHATIC BLOCK COPOLYMER ON CELLULAR ADHESION BEHAVIORS

Madoka Takai

Department of Bioengineering, The University of Tokyo, 7-3-1 Hongo Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo, Japan

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In order to create biocompatible surfaces for various tissue engineering applications, it is important to be able to control the degree of cell adhesion. One method of such control is through the topology of protein distribution on the surface. In particular, block copolymers have been shown to create phase-separated, nanoscale domains of hydrophobic and hydrophilic natures. However, precisely how the topology and polarity of the phase-separated, nanoscale structure affect the cell adhesion behavior is still unclear. Therefore, in this study, we investigate the effect of phase reversal of block copolymers composed of poly(2-methacryloyloxyethyl phosphorylcholine (MPC)) (PMPC) and poly(3-methacryloyloxy propyltris (trimethylsilyloxy) silane (MPTSSi)) (PMPTSSi), dissolved in various solvents and in different compositions, on the cell adhesion behaviors.

Plenary 4

NANO-STRUCTURED RNA FOR RNA INTERFERENCE.

Hiroshi Abe

Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Hokkaido University, Kita-12, Nishi-6, Kita-ku, Sapporo 060-0812, Japan.

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RNA interference (RNAi) is a potent and highly specific gene-silencing phenomenon which is initiated or triggered by double-stranded RNAs (dsRNAs). Shortly after the development of RNAi, small interfering RNAs (siRNAs) that are 21 nucleotides in length with a 3' nucleotide overhang were shown to be very effective in mammalian cells. Much effort has been dedicated to the application of siRNAs, both as biological tools and as therapeutic agents. These approaches can be divided into two main classes. In the first, DNA vectors encoding the RNA polymerase II or III promoter are used to transcribe siRNAs or short hairpin RNAs (shRNAs) in mammalian cells. In the second, chemically synthesized siRNA is introduced directly into cells. Although the vector system is suitable for biological

experiments, there are safety problems with clinical applications. Currently, synthetic siRNA would be the method of choice for clinical purposes. However, natural RNA strands are quickly degraded in biological fluids. Chemically synthesized unnatural nucleotides have been developed and introduced into the siRNA strand. For example, modification of the ribose moiety with a 2'-deoxy, 2'-O-methyl, or 2'-fluoro group, or modification of the phosphate backbone have been examined. Although these modifications improve the stability of siRNA in serum, they often cause a decrease in RNAi activity. There is also concern that unnatural RNA derivatives are toxic in the human body. A method to stabilize nontoxic natural RNA strands should be very useful for applications in RNAi technology. Here, we designed and synthesized circular RNA dumbbells as new RNAi technology. We designed RNA dumbbells that contained a stem sequence encoding the firefly luciferase gene and two 9-mer loops. We have demonstrated that despite being natural RNA strands, dumbbell-shaped RNAs withstand enzymatic degradation and offer prolonged RNAi activity, because of the shape of the molecule, an endless structure.

Plenary 5

MY PERSONAL HISTORY WITH INDIA

Tahei Tahara

Molecular Spectroscopy Laboratory, RIKEN, 2-1 Hirosawa, Wako, Saitama 351-0198, Japan

Email: tahei@riken.jp

My personal history with India started when a young Indian researcher and his supervisor visited my laboratory just for an hour at the Institute for Molecular Science (IMS) in Okazaki in 1996. At that time, I had just started my own laboratory as a freshman associate professor and had not published any papers yet. Nevertheless, they nicely 'discovered' me, and it has opened my door to India. Later, the young researcher became my first foreign postdoctoral fellow. His supervisor has been one of my best friends, and he later became very famous worldwide. Since then, I came to know many excellent young and senior Indian scientists. In fact, so far, I have had 9 postdoctoral fellows and 5 Ph.D. students (including short-term visitors) from India and worked with them. In this presentation, I will talk about my past and recent research in advanced laser spectroscopy using ultrashort femtosecond (10^{-15} sec) pulses, in particular, elucidation of ultrafast chemical events and molecular properties of liquid interfaces, focusing on the work that I have done with Indian coworkers.

Plenary 6

TOWARD HIGHLY EFFICIENT MOLECULAR SWITCH

Takuya Nakashima and Tsuyoshi Kawai

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There is much interest in molecular switching materials that modulate a given physical property through the action of some external trigger. Among these materials, considerable attention has focused on photochromic molecules, which undergo reversible photo- isomerization between pairs of bistable isomers with different absorption spectra upon irradiation. In particular, the photochromic molecules based on reversible 6π - electrocyclization reaction exhibit an efficient switching capability. The photo-induced 6π -electrocyclization is known to proceed only from C_2 -symmetrical conformation of the reactive hexatriene moiety. Terarylenes, which are composed of three heteroaromatic rings, offer a wide accessibility to the control of molecular folding in terms of the design of intra- and inter-molecular interactions through the combinations of various heteroaromatics.

In the present study, we propose a concept for the design of highly reactive photochromic terarylenes whose molecular structure folds into the photoreactive conformation *via* multiple intra- and inter-molecular interactions to show photon-efficient reactions. Bis(thiazolyl)- benzothiophene was designed as a representative molecule whose conformation is expected to be stabilized into the photo-reactive conformation *via* multiple intramolecular interactions.[1] The photo-reactive C_2 -like conformation was confirmed by X-ray crystallography in solid state as well as by ^1H NMR spectrum in solution. Owing to the conformational control, the molecule showed an efficient 6π -electrocyclization reaction with the topmost quantum yield, the photon-quantitative reaction. The control of molecular folding was further applied to a host-guest system. The binding of a methanol molecule to the terarylenes effectively suppressed the rotation about the aryl-aryl bond, directing the adoption of the photochromic active conformation.

Although the 6π -electrocyclization reaction should be photo-reversible, the photoinduced cycloreversion reaction was inefficient for the molecules showing efficient photocyclization reaction. We therefore introduced electrochemical stimuli as a trigger for the cycloreversion reaction. A terarylene showing the cycloreversion reaction with the efficiency of 1% exhibited very efficient cycloreversion reaction upon electrochemical oxidation. The efficiency of oxidative cycloreversion reaction was determined to be far more than 100%. The chain reaction between the long-lived oxidized colorless form and the neutral colored form was responsible for the enhancement of reaction efficiency.

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Plenary 7

INTERMETALLIC Pt₃Ti NANOPARTICLES: CO-POISONING TOLERANT ELECTROCATALYST FOR THE POLYMER-MEMBRANE ELECTROLYTE FUEL CELLS

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Efficient energy-harvesting from small molecules is becoming crucial to meet energy and environmental challenges. Polymer-electrolyte membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs) are one of the most promising technologies because they can directly convert chemical energy into electricity at a much higher efficiency than combustion engines. However, PEMFCs, in particular those using energetically dense carbon-containing fuels, have been precluded from wide practical use because the current Pt-based anode catalysts are highly susceptible to poisoning by carbon monoxide in the fuels (CO-poisoning). Herein, we report that Pt₃Ti intermetallic NPs (< 5 nm) can be synthesized via a wet-chemistry route and exhibit improved CO-poisoning tolerance and enhanced electro-oxidation activities for carbon-containing fuels, methanol and formic acid.

Plenary 8

REMARKABLE CURRENT-CARRYING-CAPACITY OF CARBON NANOTUBE-COPPER COMPOSITE

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Miniaturization has been one of the technological cornerstones driving the rapid progress and commercialization of electronic gadgets and devices. Electronic components such as transistors and memory devices have undergone a size reduction of over 10^5 times, greatly increasing their portability and ubiquity. Simultaneously, the conductors supplying power to these components have experienced an exponential increase in current flowing through them. Currently, these conductors are operating at their maximum current-carrying-capacity (ampacity) of $\sim 10^6$ A/cm². This has been a major limiting factor for development of next-generation electronics.

Addressing this, we develop an electrical conductor based on carbon nanotube and copper¹, possessing a remarkable ampacity of 10^8 A/cm². This is over 100-times higher than any existing metal, alloy or composite. This has been achieved without compromising on its electrical conductivity (4.6×10^5 S/cm), on par with copper (5.7×10^5 S/cm). Further, addition of carbon nanotubes lowers its density by 40%, making it a light-weight electrical conductor. Fundamentally, this remarkable ampacity was possible due to the carbon nanotubes suppressing the migration of copper atoms at high current densities. Experimental evidence of increased activation energy of Cu atom-migration is also presented.

Addressing practical applications for microelectronic circuits, complex, three dimensional hierarchical patterns of CNT-Cu composite has been demonstrated. This material is expected to have applications ranging from electrical power transmission cables to interconnects and vias of Integrated Chips and microelectronic circuits. Being light-weight, its advantages extend to replacing copper in aircrafts and automobiles.

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Plenary 9

DESIGN OF PEPTIDE DRUG AGAINST INFLUENZA: SELECTION OF HEMAGGLUTININ-BINDING PEPTIDES FROM RANDOM PEPTIDE LIBRARIES

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The effectiveness of vaccination is depending on the matching between influenza vaccines and circulating influenza (flu) virus. Recently, several antiviral drugs against flu such as oseltamivir and zanamivir have been developed, and these drugs are designed to inhibit one or more step of viral life cycle. However, such carbohydrate derivatives are hard to prepare and generally expensive.

Hemagglutinin (HA) protein of flu virus binds to sialylgalactose structures (Neu5Ac–Gal) in glycoproteins and glycolipids on the cell surface in the initial stage of the infection process. Matsubara *et al.* identified HA-binding peptides from peptide library by selection with HAs of the H1 and H3 subtypes. The HA-binding peptides are thought to mimic carbohydrate structure, and the alkylated peptides inhibited the infection of Madin-Darby canine kidney cells by influenza virus. A docking study of the interaction between the peptide and HA suggested that the peptide is recognized by the Neu5Ac–Gal receptor-binding pocket of HA protein. Furthermore the sugar-modified peptide was found to show the highest inhibitory activity.

These HA-binding peptides have a potential as anti-flu drugs and are able to be produce cheaply in large quantities than carbohydrate derivatives.

Plenary 10

GRAPHENE AND H-BN FORMED BY SURFACE SEGREGATION AND PRECIPITATION

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Graphene formed on hexagonal-BN basal-plane nanosheet has attracted intense interest due to its excellent electronic property such as carrier mobility. Here we introduce our synthesis and characterization methodology of graphene, graphene-based nanoscale carbon objects, and hexagonal BN (h-BN) nanosheet films. Our synthesis methods for graphene and h-BN are highly unique because conventional deposition-like growth techniques like CVD methods are not employed, but surface segregation and surface precipitation of dopants are used [1,2]. Synthesis of graphene-based nano-objects such as nanodots, nanowires, and nano-belts has been studied by our group using UHV-STM, in-situ AES, XPS and other surface analytical tools [3-6]. For example, by surface precipitation of C dopants in Pt-, Pd-, or Ni-based substrates, mono-, bi- and multi-layer graphene have been prepared successfully [7,8]. As for graphene characterization, Raman spectroscopy has been used as a standard technique to identify monolayer, bilayer, and few-layer graphene, where quality of graphene films can be evaluated by the presence of a defect-induced D band and the position and shape of G and G' bands. However, since the Raman spectroscopic features of graphene films are strongly influenced by the substrate materials, it may be difficult to characterize the layer numbers on metal substrates in general. We have demonstrated that Scanning Auger Microscopy (SAM) can be a quantitative analytical technique for the identification of layers of graphene and h-BN films at the nanoscale [9]. Recently we succeeded in the synthesis of h-BN nanosheets on transition metal alloy substrates doped with B and N elements, using surface segregation and reaction to form h-BN(0001) basal planes.

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Plenary 11

GRAIN REFINEMENT OF MAGNESIUM ALLOYS FOR IMPROVING MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE

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Magnesium alloys are being widely investigated throughout the world for the weight reduction of structural components due to their low density. In structural applications, the strength of magnesium alloys should be increased along with their ductility to improve the relatively low stiffness, so that the alloys can be formed into complex shapes. One of the major microstructural factors for strengthening of metals is grain refinement. It is even more effective in increasing the strength of magnesium alloys because of the relatively large Taylor factor in its HCP structure compared to that of the other lightweight metal, aluminum. The tensile elongation also increases with grain refinement due to the enhanced activity of grain boundary sliding and/or non-basal slip. Another important factor for enhancing the ductility is the distribution of the basal plane orientation, *i.e.*, the basal texture. The basal texture can be modified by changing the applied shear loading direction during severe plastic working, and/or by changing the recrystallization behavior by a combination of distributing nano-scale particles and plastic working.

In the present study, grain refinement with a weakened texture was demonstrated for a commercial Mg-Al-Zn alloy by applying a repetitive oblique shear strain using caliber rolling, which can operate continuously at a commercial processing speed and commercial scale. The applied severe plastic working refined the grain structure effectively in sub-micro-meter scale and resulted in a high yield stress of over 400 MPa. A simultaneous operation of oblique shear strain weakened the basal texture from that of the initial as-extruded alloy and resulted in a certain tensile ductility comparable to the commercially extruded alloy and a higher asymmetry ratio of yield stress in compression/tension (0.82) than that of the as-extruded alloy (0.57). Another merit of refining the grain structure will be also addressed for biomedical implant applications.

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Plenary 12

MITIGATION OF VEHICULAR POLLUTANTS FOR CLEAN ENVIRONMENT

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Pollution caused by automobile emissions is an issue of great concern and is the subject of extensive research for the past several decades. With the rapid growth in the urbanization in the developing countries that lead to increase in motor vehicle usage and , the amount of pollutants emitting from vehicles is steadily increasing despite modern engine technologies. The exhaust emitted from automotive engines contains three primary gaseous pollutants, nitrogen oxides (NO_x), unburned hydrocarbons (HC) and carbon monoxide (CO) and the soot particulates. The emission of the above pollutants leads to many environmental and health problems. If the vehicular emissions continue as usual, significant amount of the world's population will be subject to degraded air quality in 2050

Governments across the globe have introduced stringent legislations to curb pollutants in the exhaust of automotive engines. One such measure which is imperative in the modern vehicles is the use of catalyst based exhaust aftertreatment cleaning devices. Today catalysts play a critical role in the operation of almost all the automotive vehicles for example, three way catalyst (TWC) technology in gasoline engines and diesel oxidation catalyst (DOC) and selective catalytic reduction (SCR) technologies in diesel engines.

The presentation covers a review of automotive emission trends in mature markets (such as Japan and US) and emerging markets (such as BRIC countries) and catalyst based control technologies that are being developed in our laboratory that can be potentially employed in the mitigation of nitrogen oxide (NO_x) pollution control.

4th ISAJ India-Japan symposium on Emerging Materials, 11 Oct., 2013, Tokyo, Japan.

P1

SEX MANIPULATION BY MICROBES -ARE YOU MALE OR FEMALE?

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In most animals and plants, sex determination is one of the most important developmental processes. Although sex chromosome constitution (e.g., XY or XX) usually determines their sexes, some exceptions exist; heritable (but non-infectious) microbes living within the body of some invertebrates can transform genetically male individuals into females. These feminized individuals are not only morphologically but also functionally complete females. By focusing on the relationship between a butterfly *Eurema mandarina* and its symbiotic bacterium *Wolbachia pipientis*, I try to understand the molecular mechanism underlying the microbe-induced sex manipulation using an insect cell culture system and next-generation sequencing technologies. Although *Eurema* butterflies commonly occur in mainland and southern island of Japan as well as in India, *Wolbachia* with a feminizing effect has only been found in southern islands of Japan. Intriguingly, because of the prevalence of the feminizing *Wolbachia*, *Eurema* butterfly populations in Tanegashima Island are subjected to an extreme sex ratio bias toward female. The scarcity of males resulted in low mating frequency, which is likely to profoundly affect population maintenance of this butterfly. In this talk, I will also mention a possible idea that explains why *Wolbachia* feminize males despite the risk to go extinct together with its host.

P2

HIGH TEMPERATURE SHAPE MEMORY BEHAVIOUR OF Ti-50Pd-2.5Zr-2.5Hf ALLOY

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The binary Ti-Pd alloys, at near equiatomic compositions, transform from cubic B2 austenitic phase to orthorhombic B19 martensitic phase in the temperature range of 400 to 600°C. The exhibition of unique shape memory behavior associated with this transformation makes them to consider for functional applications in that temperature range. However, binary alloys were found to have poor strength, as low as 50 MPa, just above their austenite finish temperature that shapely deteriorates the shape memory properties makes them not suitable for the applications. Alloying has been suggested to improve the strength of the binary alloys. Our recent investigation utilizing this method showed that Zr, Hf, and V additions were effective. The purpose of present study is particularly to find the combined effect of Zr and Hf on high temperature mechanical and shape memory properties of Ti-Pd alloy.

The ingot of Ti-50Pd-2.5Zr-2.5Hf (at. %) alloy weighing 15 g was prepared by vacuum arc melting of pure elemental powders followed by homogenization at 1000 °C for a week. The homogenized alloy has a microstructure of B19 martensite with (Ti, Hf, Zr)₂Pd particles on grain boundaries. The Af and Mf temperatures, as measured by DSC, were 510 and 423 °C, respectively. The yield strength of martensite was measured by compression test at Mf-30 °C and was about 1140 MPa. The strength of austenite at Af+30 °C was about 378 MPa which was significantly higher than the alloys contain either only Zr (274 MPa) or Hf (267 MPa). Shape memory strain was 1.6% with 80% shape recovery. The shape memory behavior was also studied by load-bias thermal cycle experiments. Specimen showed open loop strain-temperature curves during first thermal cycle; however upon training closed loop curves were obtained. From these curves work output corresponding to one way shape memory effect was calculated. The properties of present alloy will be compared with alloys prepared only with Zr or Hf thereby influence of combined addition will be addressed.

P3

ELUCIDATING THE WATER STRUCTURE AT NONIONIC LIPID/WATER INTERFACES USING NOVEL INTERFACE SELECTIVE NONLINEAR SPECTROSCOPY

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Despite its importance in many processes of biological relevance, our understanding of lipid/water interfaces remains rather insufficient. This is chiefly due to difficulties in experimentally detecting and characterizing such interfaces with sufficient molecular level sensitivity. Heterodyne-detected vibrational sum frequency generation (HD-VSFG) is a novel interface selective nonlinear spectroscopic technique that allows us to overcome these constraints and obtain useful insights into lipid/water interfaces. The HD-VSFG experiment is capable of determining the net orientation of water molecules at a given interface [1]. The sign of the OH stretch band as revealed in the imaginary $\chi^{(2)}$ spectrum of interfacial water provides vital information about the absolute orientation of water molecules at the interface under investigation. Using HD-VSFG, we have previously studied interfaces between water and ionic lipids and clarified the orientation and hydrogen-bond structure of water at these ionic lipid/water interfaces [2]. In this work, we extend our HD-VSFG study of lipid/water interfaces and study the structure of water at a nonionic lipid/water interface.

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P4

THE EFFECT OF PRECIPITATION STRENGTHENING ON SLIP AND TWINNING IN A Mg-Zn ALLOY

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Transportation is a major contributor to world-wide greenhouse gas emissions. Established and emerging economies now face the difficult challenge of balancing stable economic growth for an expanding population with the urgent need to curtail emissions in the face of anthropogenic climate change. Reducing vehicle weight plays an important part in improving efficiency and cutting transport-based emissions. This offers not only incremental improvements in vehicle efficiency, but can be vital to ensure the viability of technologies such as hybrid vehicles. Recent years have seen a growing trend towards the replacement of steel components with lighter aluminium and, more recently, magnesium alloys. The development of strong and durable magnesium alloys is thus of vital importance.

Magnesium alloys can be strengthened by using heat-treatment to introduce a fine dispersion of nanoscale precipitates. These precipitates are highly effective at preventing deformation via dislocations. However, even very fine dispersions of hard particles appear to be of limited effectiveness at preventing deformation by the formation and growth of crystallographic twins. This process results in weak and non-uniform mechanical properties and restricting or preventing its occurrence is a key challenge. This work examines how nano-scale precipitates in a Mg-Zn alloy affect deformation by slip and twinning. Using a combination of heat-treatment and controlled deformation it has been possible to compare the effectiveness of different distributions of particles on each deformation mechanism. The microstructure has been examined at different stages to quantify the size and number density of precipitates and relate this information to the mechanical properties. It was found that although precipitates helped the alloy resist twinning, changing the size and spacing of the particles had little effect. This was in contrast to the effect on deformation by dislocations. The differences were largely attributable to the morphology of the precipitates.

P5

SELF ASSEMBLY AND CIRCULARLY POLARIZED LUMINESCENCE OF CHIRAL BICHROMOPHORIC PERYLENE BISIMIDES

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Circularly Polarized Luminescence (CPL) is emerging as a powerful tool for probing the electronic structure of chiral molecular systems.¹ The interest in the development of efficient electronic devices based on organic materials has further enhanced the significance of the spectroscopic technique.^{1a} More recently, the technique has been utilized for investigating the excited state properties of helically self-assembled molecular aggregates^{1b} and Spano and co-workers have theoretically predicted significant enhancement of CPL dissymmetry in the π -stacked helicites with highly ordered chromophores.^{1c}

In the present work, we investigate the helical supramolecular assembly of two highly emissive and CPL active trans-1,2-diamide-cyclohexane derivatives, bearing two perylenebisimides arranged in a chiral fashion.² The bichromophoric system exhibited CPL with dissymmetry factors typical to that of similar organic chiral chromophoric systems in the monomeric state. Variation in solvent composition led to the formation of stably soluble helical aggregates through intermolecular interactions. A large enhancement in the dissymmetry of CPL was exhibited from the aggregated structures both in the solution and solid states. The sum of excitonic couplings between the individual chromophoric units in the self-assembled state, results in relatively large dissymmetry in the CPL giving rise to enhanced g_{lum} values for the aggregated structures. The spacer between chiral center and chromophoric units played a crucial role in the effective enhancement of chiroptical properties in the aggregated structures.² These materials may provide opportunities for the design of new class of functional organic nanoarchitectures that can find potential applications in field of chiroptical memory and light emitting devices.

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P6

SYNTHESIS OF $K_8Al_xSi_{46-x}$: NEW THERMOELECTRIC CLATHRATE COMPOUND

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Recently ternary type-I Si clathrate $K_8Ga_8Si_{38}$ has been revealed to be a semiconductor [1], in contrast to the other ternary type-I Si clathrates including alkaline-earth metals such as $Ba_8Ga_xSi_{46-x}$ and $Sr_8Al_xSi_{46-x}$ which show metallic conduction. $K_8Ga_8Si_{38}$ has attracted attentions as a material for energy conversion including solar-cell application or thermoelectric application. From view point of sustainability of raw material supply, it is better to use Al instead of Ga because Al is more abundant in the earth crust. We report here synthesis of new ternary clathrate compound $K_8Al_xSi_{46-x}$. The compound is synthesized by solid state reaction route at atmospheric pressure. In the series of synthesis of several other ternary phases we have been able to synthesize this compound. Excess of K is used due to its volatile nature. It is also observed that excess of Al is required, in order to obtain the phase pure compound. Rietveld refinement of X-Ray diffraction pattern is carried out in order check the phase purity. Minor impurity peak of Al with few untraced peaks have been also seen. The compound is crystallized in $Pm\bar{3}n$ cubic space group with lattice parameter $a = 10.45(3) \text{ \AA}$. The thermoelectric properties studies are under way. This research was partially supported by the *JST ALCA* program.

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P8

SYNTHESIS AND STUDIES OF NOVEL MULTI-FUNCTIONAL POLYMER COATINGS FOR METALS AND ALLOYS

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The synthesis of novel materials with improved properties and performance is an emerging and challenging field at the interface of chemistry and materials science. In this context, polymer coatings have demonstrated as a reliable method for creating smart surfaces with anti-corrosion, anti-biofouling, controllable wettability, friction, and stimuli responsiveness, which lead to potential applications in biosensors, microfluidic devices, nanoactuation, long-lasting structural materials, and others.¹ Developing versatile, strong, and widely applicable binding interaction between the polymer chains and various substrates is very important in this process. Biomimetic catechol-containing compound (dopamine) which is common in adhesive foot proteins of several marine organisms like mussels, hydroids, and tubeworms, have been reported to show good binding affinity towards almost all kind of materials like metals, metal oxides, ceramics, or synthetic polymers.²

However, further applications of such polymers have been limited owing to easy oxidation of catechol units to non-binding quinone state in basic conditions leading to decomposition of the surface coating. To overcome this shortcoming, we focus to prepare dopamide and 1,2-glycol containing organic polymers and compare their binding properties to various metal substrates such as Mg-alloy, Ti, Pt, Al, Au, Ag, *etc.* Here we expected that the catechol/glycol units exhibit good adhesion property through multiple co-ordinations binding with two hydroxyl groups and intermolecular hydrogen bonding among urethane unit. The catechol/glycol monomer having methacrylate unit was homo-polymerized or co-polymerized with several co-monomers (methyl methacrylate, hexyl methacrylate, dodecyl methacrylate, *n*-isopropylacrylamide *etc.*) by free radical polymerization using AIBN as radical initiator. These polymers were purified and well characterized by NMR spectra, FT-IR, MALDI-TOF-MS, and GPC. After that, these polymers were coated on metal substrates by dip-coating or spin-coating method by changing different conditions like time, temperature, and pH. Immobilization of these polymers on various substrates was primarily studied by SEM, XPS, ATR-IR, and also stability of the film at ambient conditions were thoroughly investigated. Further, we intend to check anti-corrosion, anti-fouling, or other interesting properties of such polymer coated metals/alloys substrates.

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P9

BIOCHAR INFLUENCING METHANE FLUX IN PADDY ECOSYSTEM

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Biochar is believed to have a positive impact on the soil properties and plant yield [1]. Due to the presence of C, it can also enhance CH₄ emission in paddy soils. Keeping these points in view, a microcosm experiment was conducted to determine the effect of various concentrations of biochar on CH₄ emission and methanogenic community in paddy vegetated soil. Biogas digested liquid was used as N source @ 120 kg N/ha in each treated soil. Biogas digested liquid has been proposed as an alternate to chemical fertilizer in our previous study [2]. In the present study, four treatments in triplicate were as follows: 1) Control: without biochar; 2) BL, biochar @ 180 kg C/ha (C/N 1.5); 3) BM, biochar @ 360 kg C/ha (C/N 3.0); 4) BH, biochar @ 720 kg C/ha (C/N 6.0). Biochar was applied as basal dose only; while N was applied in 3 split doses in each treated soil. The addition of biochar increased CH₄ emission than untreated soil and it significantly increased with increase in biochar concentration. Biochar application increased soluble organic content of the soil. It also increased NH₄⁺-N content of soils probably by providing more reducible conditions in soils. Biochar application decreased NO₃⁻-N content of soils. Denaturing gradient gel electrophoresis showed no differences in banding pattern for methanogens which suggested no change in methanogenic community in biochar treated soils or untreated soil. Biochar application had positive impact on plant variables such as shoot weight, panicle number and weight of panicles. Plant biomass increased with increase in biochar concentration but differences were not significantly different between BM and BH treated containers.

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P10

EFFECT OF WITHAFERIN A AND METHOXY-WITHAFERIN A IN HUMAN CANCER CELLS: BIOINFORMATICS AND BIOCHEMICAL INSIGHTS

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Alcoholic extract of Ashwagandha leaves is rich in withanolides that include withanolide D, hydroxywithanolide E, withanolide A, withaferin A, methoxy-withaferin A and withanone. Most of these are toxic to human cancer cells. Molecular mechanism of such cytotoxicity has not been completely understood. Withanone and withaferin A were earlier shown to activate p53 tumor suppressor and oxidative stress pathways in cancer cells. We investigated the effect of withaferin A (WA) and its methoxy-derivative (mWA) on human cancer and normal cells.

The modeled three-dimensional structures of WA and mWA when docked with the substrate-binding domain of mortalin, p53 and NRF2 revealed the interaction of both WA and mWA with the same residues in each of these target proteins. However, mWA was less efficient both in terms of binding energy and number of hydrogen bonding interactions. Cell culture studies demonstrated that whereas WA was cytotoxic to cancer cells at 0.6-1.0 µg/ml, mWA required 10-fold higher doses. Analysis of p53 and oxidative stress pathways further endorsed that WA is more active than its methoxy-derivative in cancer cell killing. The study demonstrated that the cytotoxic activity of natural withanolides is tightly controlled by their structure and interaction with the target proteins. Small modifications such as methylation of withaferin A could have major impact on its binding efficacy to the target proteins and cellular outcomes.

P11

INVOLVEMENT OF MicroRNAs IN HUMAN CANCER CELLS SENESCENCE

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MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are a class of non-coding small RNAs that act as negative regulators of gene expression. To identify miRNAs that may regulate human cell senescence, we explored 5Aza-dC induced senescence in human osteosarcoma cells as a model, in conjunction with induction of miRNAs library expression by random insertion of a retroviral GFP vector capable of driving the transcription of downstream genomic sequences. Such system provided a library of miRNAs and allowed the identification of candidates involved in the escape of 5AZA-dC induced senescence. miRNA microarray analysis of control and 5AZA-dC treated cells that escaped senescence revealed overexpression of several miRNA including miR-101, miR-143, miR-145, miR-335, miR-451, miR-545 and miR-558. In order to investigate the role of these miRNAs and their targets, we overexpressed them in cancer cells and examined their effect on cell cycle progression, cell cycle regulatory genes and malignant properties of cancer cells. We demonstrate that the overexpression of most of these miRNAs resulted in cell cycle arrest that may explain how the cells escaped 5AZA-dC effect that depends on its incorporation during DNA replication. Furthermore, we report that the miR-101, miR-143, miR-145, miR-335 and miR-545 targeted CAREF, an upstream regulator of p53 pathway that has been shown to be involved in execution of senescence in human cancer and normal cells.

P12

**ANTI-APOPTOTIC PROTEINS Bcl-2 AND Bcl-xL INTERACT WITH MORTALIN IN
CANCER CELLS RESULTING IN p53 ACTIVATION**

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Bcl-2 family of proteins consists of both pro-apoptotic and anti-apoptotic members that control cellular apoptosis. They predominantly reside in mitochondria and control the release of apoptotic factors from mitochondria to cytosol by regulating its membrane potential and opening the permeability transition pore. Here, we report bioinformatics and biochemical evidences to demonstrate the interaction between Bcl-2 and Bcl-xL with a stress chaperone, mortalin. Molecular docking studies revealed mortalin residues 373, 376, 377, 380, 381, 382, 283, 284, 386, 387 as residues of interface. Similarly, residues 116, 229, 92, 95, 118, 226, 113 and 15, 18, 19, 21, 213, 214, 216, 226, 229, 230 were identified as the residues of interface for Bcl-2 and Bcl-xL proteins, respectively. Analysis of mortalin-Bcl-2 docked complexes using Protorp server illustrated the presence of 17 hydrogen bonds and 48 salt-bridges at the interface. Biochemical studies using co-immunoprecipitation demonstrated that mortalin amino acid residues 310-390 are involved in its binding to Bcl-2 and Bcl-xL proteins. Furthermore, we found that Bcl-2/Bcl-xL overexpressing cells have decreased level of mortalin and increased level of p53 expression. We demonstrate that Bcl-2/Bcl-xL proteins compete with p53 for binding to mortalin and hence their overexpression results in abrogation of mortalin-p53 interaction leading to nuclear translocation and transcriptional reactivation of p53 function that results in an induction of senescence in cancer cells.

P13

CARF OVEREXPRESSION-MEDIATED GROWTH ARREST OF CANCER CELLS INVOLVE p53 PROTEIN

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Collaborator of ARF (CARF) has been shown to bind to ARF, p53 and HDM2 resulting in activation of p53-p21 pathway. Overexpression of CARF was shown to cause growth arrest of osteosarcoma (U2OS) that harbors wild type p53 function. Its knockdown caused apoptosis suggesting that it is an essential survival protein. In order to investigate the critical involvement of p53 in CARF-induced growth arrest, we used p53-null (Saos-2) cells. Most surprisingly, we found that CARF overexpression (OE) in these cells lead to increase in proliferation rate and malignant transformation as revealed by *in vitro* and *in vivo* assays. Molecular analysis revealed that CARF caused activation of ATM/ATR/CHK1/CHK2 pathway and DNA damage response in p53-compromised cells, similar to the one observed for p53-functional cells. We observed that pERK1/2 was upregulated in CARF-OE Saos-2 cells that showed higher proliferation capacity as compared to the controls. In sharp contrast, CARF-OE U2OS cells that were growth arrested showed downregulation of pERK1/2. Furthermore, treatment of CARF-OE Saos-2 cells with ERK1/2 inhibitors caused decrease in their proliferation rate suggesting that the activation of ERK1/2 was involved in increase in proliferation caused by CARF-OE in Saos-2 cells. We next investigated if activation of ERK1/2 in Saos-2/CARF OE was due to the lack of pRB and p53. Whereas reconstitution of pRB did not cause significant change in the cell proliferation phenotype, p53 reconstitution resulted in CARF induced growth arrest.

P14

ROLE OF hnRNP-k IN CANCER METASTASIS

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Metastasis is the movement of cancer cells from their primary site to elsewhere in the body and possess difficulties in cancer treatment. Identification of factors leading to metastasis hence is highly important for effective cancer therapeutics. We previously identified heterogeneous nuclear ribonucleoprotein K (hnRNP-K) protein as involved in cell migration by loss-of-function screening using intracellular antibody library (Inoue et al. Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA, 2007, 104: 8983-8). We undertook detailed *in vitro* and *in vivo* analyses to dissect the role of hnRNP-K in cancer cell migration. We established hnRNP-K over-expressing and under-expressing derivative cell lines and examined their proliferation and metastatic properties *in vitro* and *in vivo*. We report that whereas hnRNP-K compromised cells have delayed tumor growth, over-expressing derivatives exhibit enhanced malignancy and metastasis. Molecular basis of the hnRNP-K induced malignant and metastatic phenotypes were dissected by cDNA microarray and pathway analyses. We found that the hnRNP-K regulates extracellular matrix, cell motility and angiogenesis pathways. Involvement of the selected genes (CCK, MMP3, PTGS2 and CTGF) and pathways was validated by gene specific expression analysis. Our results demonstrated that the hnRNP-K is a potential target for therapy of metastatic cancer cell.

P15

NON-MITOCHONDRIAL MORTALIN PROMOTES HUMAN TUMORIGENESIS THROUGH ACTIVATION OF TELOMERASE AND hnRNP-K

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Hsp70 family protein, mortalin, is an essential chaperone that is frequently enriched in cancer cells and exists in various subcellular sites including mitochondria, plasma membrane, ER and cytosol. In the present study, we have generated mortalin mutants that lack mitochondrial targeting signal peptide. Overexpression of the non-mitochondrial mortalin in cancer cells resulted in an increase in their malignant properties *in vitro* and *in vivo* assays. Cells overexpressing non-mitochondrial mortalin protein showed higher colony forming efficiency and faster mobility in cell transformation and cell invasion assays, respectively. In nude mice assays, breast carcinoma cells overexpressing full-length mortalin formed tumors in comparison to control that were non-tumorigenic. Remarkably, we found that the non-mitochondrial mortalin-overexpressing cells were malignantly transformed, forming very aggressive, multiple and metastatic tumors. These data suggested that the mitochondrial localization of mortalin is not essential for its role in tumor progression. Molecular analysis revealed an existence of mortalin in the nucleus of a variety of human malignant cell lines. We demonstrate that the nuclear mortalin caused strong inactivation of tumor suppressor protein p53 resulting in aneuploid cells. Furthermore, it interacts with (i) telomerase resulting in stabilization and activation of its function and (ii) heterogeneous ribonucleoprotein-K (hnRNP-K) resulting in an activation of its downstream signal leading to aggressively malignant and metastatic cancer cells.

P16

REGULATION OF EPIDERMAL CELL PROLIFERATION UNDER STRESS CONDITIONS

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Plant growth retards when they face biotic or abiotic stresses. This is not solely because they cannot grow normally under stress, but at least in part this is an adaptive response. We examined stress-induced changes in leaf epidermal growth as the whole developmental pathway of Arabidopsis epidermis is well characterized. At an early stage of leaf development, a fraction of cells acquire the meristemoid mother cell (MMC)-identity initiating the stomatal lineage, which eventually produces guard and non-guard epidermal cells. EPF2-expression represents the early stomatal lineage cells (ESLCs) including MMC. We found that osmotic stress quickly decreased the number of ESLCs, and then decreased the number of both guard and non-guard epidermal cells. This effect depended on the MAP kinase activity. We found that the protein level of *SPEECHLESS*, which is required for the ESLC identity, was quickly decreased by the osmotic stress. Decrease in SPCH was mediated through MAPK. A gene for a secretory peptide mediator, *STOMAGEN*, which positively regulates the stomatal density, was repressed by osmotic stress, but *STOMAGEN* repression was not responsible for decrease in cell proliferation. Because ABA is known to be an important mediator of osmotic stress signaling, we examined the epidermal cell number in ABA-biosynthetic mutants. The results indicated that ABA is, in part, responsible for the decrease in cell proliferation under osmotic-stress. Consistent to this, exogenous application of ABA quickly decreased the number of ESLCs and decreased the SPCHpro::*SPCH*::*GFP* signal. This effect appears to be independent from the MAP kinase cascade. Based on these results, we propose a model in which osmotic stress decreases the SPCH level and decreases epidermal cell-proliferation, in ABA dependent and independent pathways. The ABA-independent pathway regulates epidermal growth by regulating SPCH via a MAPK cascade. In contrast ABA-dependent pathway function independent of SPCH. This is the first report showing that plants decrease a master regulator for stem cell maintenance, thereby undergo adaptive developmental regulation, when they face osmotic stress.

P17

FLAME RETARDANCY OF VERMICULITE COMPOSITE COATINGS ON WOOD

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Vermiculite- a hydrated magnesium aluminum silicate clay mineral is an expandable layered structure. Exfoliated layers of vermiculite have been widely used in various fields owing to its important applications such as light weight, low density, thermal stability, etc. In this study, coating of exfoliated vermiculite and vermiculite composites on wooden substrate and their flame resistance behavior is tested with the help of cone calorimetric analysis. Vermiculite and composite materials are characterized by powder XRD, FTIR, TGA, SEM-EDX and XRF analyses. The detailed results will be discussed.

P18

EFFECT OF AGING ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF Ti-Mo ALLOY

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Over the last few decades, the titanium alloys have been playing an important role in aerospace, chemistry, biomedical and other applications due to their high specific strength, good corrosion resistance and excellent hardenability. Among the recently developed Titanium alloys, the metastable β -Ti alloys with body-centered cubic (bcc) crystal structure seem to present a promising combination of mechanical and physical properties. For example, the Ti-10V-2Fe-3Al alloy is widely used throughout the Boeing 777 airplane, in the wings, fuselage, doors, nacelles and cargo handling structures. The thermo-mechanical parameters could have significant effects on the properties of material such as temperature and time of heat treatment, ageing sequence and the deformation rate. In this study, the effect of aging on the mechanical properties was investigated for the future improvement.

The aim of the study is to find the effects of aging treatment of the mechanical properties on the metastable β Ti-Mo alloy. In the experiment, the binary Ti-12Mo (mass %) alloy was researched. The ingot material was prepared by the cold crucible levitation melting (CCLM), then hot forged and hot rolled to square bar followed by air cooling. The rolled bar was solution treated (ST) at 1073K for 3.6 ks

followed by water quenching, to obtain the β single phase sample with equiaxed grains. As comparison, half of the materials after ST were moved to aging treatment at 523 K for 3.6 ks followed by water quenching, named as STA. Frost et al. in 1954 found that there would be ω phase precipitation in some β -Ti alloys during ageing period at low temperature. As for the measurements of mechanical properties at room temperature, the uniaxial tensile test was carried out for the strength and plasticity, and the V-notch charpy impact test was to check the notch toughness.

The results showed that the tensile strength of ST samples could reach to around 720 MPa while the uniform elongation was about 50%, compared with that of the STA sample (13%), with the significant improved tensile strength at about 1030 MPa. As for the V-notch charpy impact test, the value of fracture absorbed energy of ST was about 180 J which was more than 10 times larger than STA sample. The aged ω -phase enhanced the tensile strength but with a loss of ductility and fracture absorbed energy in charpy impact tests.

P19

EFFECT OF ZIRCONIUM AND COBALT ADDITION ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF HIGH TEMPERATURE TITANIUM ALLOY

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Titanium alloys, are extensively used in jet engines as compressor discs and blades due to their light weight and superior fatigue and creep properties at elevated temperatures. However the maximum temperature is limited to 600°C. It would be very useful, if a new Ti alloys with improved mechanical properties, creep resistance, ductility and workability above 600°C has developed.

Various methods have been proposed to enhance high temperature properties of the alloys. Alloying is one of the important methods. In the present study the effect of Zr and Co addition on room temperature and high temperature mechanical properties of near alpha Ti alloy was investigated.

The compression test results showed that Zr addition significantly improves both room temperature and high temperature strength. Zr addition reduces the solubility of Si in Ti alloy and form complex silicide, which improves mechanical properties at room temperature and at high temperature.

Room temperature compression strength was not significantly altered by Co addition, however the ductility is slightly reduced, due to the precipitation of Co. The high temperature compression strength was drastically reduced due to Co addition. The results obtained were explained based on the microstructural examination.

P20

ENHANCED AMORPHIZATION BY INCREASING DEFORMATION TEMPERATURE IN Zr-Cu-Al ALLOYS

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Amorphous materials are characterized by absence of long-range order in the atomic arrangements, resulting in high strength and good corrosion resistance [1]. Besides rapid quenching of the melts to a frozen liquid structure, crystal-to-amorphous transformation induced by severe plastic deformation (SPD) is also regarded as effective method to fabricate amorphous materials. High-pressure torsion (HPT), as one kind of SPD techniques, has attracted extensive attentions since ultrahigh plastic deformation can be applied on ductile or brittle alloys without changing the shapes. Temperature increase during the HPT deformation is believed to be very small (25 K in pure iron after 10 revolutions under a pressure of 2 GPa and rotation speed 1 rpm) and therefore negligible [2]. However, since the temperature rise is measured from the attached anvils but not from the sample directly, the local temperature in the sample may be higher and it would be interesting to investigate the effect of deformation temperature on amorphization process during HPT. In the present study, we investigated the effect of deformation temperature on the amorphization during HPT.

Crystallized Zr₅₀Cu₅₀ (Al0) and Zr₅₀Cu₄₄Al₆ (Al6) samples were deformed by HPT with compressive pressure of 5 GPa at a rotation speed of 1 rpm to 10 and 20 revolutions under different temperatures. Thermal couple embedded in the upper anvil was used to record the temperature evolution during HPT. The cross-section of the deformed samples was prepared for optical microscopic (OM) observations. X-ray diffraction (XRD) was used to characterize phase configuration. Samples for transmission electron microscopy (TEM) observations were cut from the position with their centers at around 3.5 mm from the center of the disk.

XRD analysis revealed that crystalline-to-amorphous transformation was achieved by HPT in both Al0 and Al6 alloys, but the amorphization processing showed marked temperature dependence. Increasing deformation temperature significantly enhances the transformation from crystalline-to-amorphous phases.

One possible reason for this behavior can be the lattice instability near the starting temperature of reverse martensitic transformation. Another possible explanation may be that the atomic diffusion is easier at higher temperature, which accelerates the transformation from crystalline phase with high density of defects to amorphous structures during HPT deformation.

Increasing the HPT processing temperature remarkably enhances formation of amorphous phase, while further increase induces crystallization of amorphous phase. The present results suggests the need for a careful consideration of temperature effect on microstructural evolution during HPT, and provide important clues for understanding the amorphization behavior induced by plastic deformation.

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P21

MOLECULAR INSIGHTS INTO THE RESIDUES RESPONSIBLE FOR SEROTYPE SPECIFICITY AND CROSS-REACTIVITY IN DENGUE

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Dengue (DEN) viruses are classified into four serotypes. Subsequent infection with a different serotype causes severe Dengue hemorrhagic fever. There is no effective drug or vaccine available to overcome this dreadful disease. DEN virus structural protein consists of a capsid protein, a membrane protein and a major envelope glycoprotein. The envelope protein domain III (ED3) of DEN contains the two putative epitope regions, which are responsible for serotype specificity and cross-reactivity. Overall ED3 of different serotypes show high structural similarity but minute local structural differences at few sites are thought to be responsible for serotype specificity.

Here, we report a mutational analysis of the two epitopes and analyzed the results using the high resolution crystal structure of bacterially expressed ED3 of DEN3 and DEN4. We designed six ED3 variants where putative epitope1 (E1) and epitope2 (E2) of ED3 were grafted, both individually and in combination, from DEN3 on to DEN4 and vice-versa. Secondary structure content and stability analysis using CD showed that mutants in whom only E2 has been grafted are more stable than mutants in which only E1 or both E1 and E2 were grafted. These observations were further corroborated with indirect ELISA studies which showed that wild type ED3 of DEN3 and DEN4 generated increased specific responses with Monoclonal antibody (Mab) DEN3 and Mab DEN4 respectively. However, grafting of the E2 exhibited DEN3 and DEN4 cross reactive responses indicating that few residues residing at E2 could be major determinants of serotype specificity. Further immunological and mutational studies may help to explore the DEN serotype determinant at atomic level.

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P22

EFFECT OF Si AND Ge ON THE EVOLUTION OF MICROSTRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES IN NEAR ALPHA TITANIUM ALLOY

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Near alpha titanium alloys with minor amount of Si content has shown considerable improvement in strength, creep resistance, and oxidation resistance. Earlier studies have shown that Ge added titanium silicides improve thermal stability. In order to improve their high temperature performance, Si and Ge were added to titanium alloys and their effects on the evolution of microstructure and mechanical properties are investigated.

Near alpha titanium alloys of nominal composition Ti-5Al-2Sn-4Zr-2Mo with different amount of Si and Ge were prepared. The alloys were beta forged at 1100°C, and hot rolled at 960°C to 50% reductions. The hot rolled alloys were given an annealing treatment at 950°C for 3 hrs and subsequent ageing treatment at 590°C for 8hrs. The microstructure of the processed material was analyzed in terms of fraction of lamellar, equi-axed and precipitates to understand the effect of different solute elements. Precipitates were of either (Ti,Zr)₆Si₃ or (Ti,Zr)₆Ge₃ type with large variation in the solute content, suggesting that they are off-stoichiometric. Vickers micro hardness of the material was obtained at different processing conditions to understand the effect of microstructure on mechanical properties.

P23

HIGHLY ACTIVE AND STABLE INTERMETALLIC Pt₃Ta NANOSTRUCTURE FOR THE METHANOL AND ETHANOL FUEL CELLS AND EXHAUST NO GAS PURIFICATION

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Pt and other noble metals have been efficiently used as heterogeneous catalysts in several catalytic processes such as exhaust purification (NO_x reduction) and direct alcohol fuel cells (DAFC).¹ The critical issues that limit the utilization of Pt as efficient catalyst for DAFC and exhaust gas purification are the high cost of Pt, its limited content in the earth's crust and deterioration of its catalytic activity.² Therefore, it is important to develop new catalysts that reduce overall use of Pt, and exhibit higher activity

and stability toward different catalytic reactions. Pt-based bimetallic nanoparticles have emerged as efficient catalysts because of the enhanced activity of Pt that is promoted by the presence of the second atom while keeping the amount of platinum less. Here, we present our strategy to synthesize intermetallic Pt₃Ta nanoparticles by a wet-chemical method followed by their detailed characterization using different characterization techniques. We compare their electrochemical activity towards methanol and ethanol electrooxidation with the activity of commercially available Pt/C catalyst. The electrocatalytic activity of the intermetallic Pt₃Ta nanoparticles is found to be several times higher than that of Pt/C. In addition to this, the Pt₃Ta nanoparticles exhibit higher CO tolerance and stability in comparison with that of Pt/C. Most interestingly, intermetallic Pt₃Ta nanoparticles also show high activity in NO_x reduction by CO with excellent selectivity for N₂. We believe that the combined effect of modification of the electronic structure of Pt and the bi-functional mechanism promoted by the presence of Ta are responsible for the greater catalytic activity.

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P24

FORMATION OF INTRINSIC-1 LPSO PHASE IN A Mg-Co-Y ALLOY

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Mg-Zn-Y alloy forms synchronized long period stacking/ordered (LPSO) phase. LPSO structures are long period stacking variants of the hexagonal close packed atomic layers. So far four polytypes, 10H, 18R, 14H and 24R have been reported. LPSO structures are systematically described by introducing intrinsic-2 type stacking fault periodically into 2H stacking. Zn/Y enrich at four particular close-packed layers relevant to faulting of original 2H stacking. LPSO structures are also formed in several Mg-TM-RE alloy (TM= Zn, Cu, Ni and Al, RE= Y, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er and Tm). We investigate Mg-Co-Y alloy and find novel type of LPSO structure in a Mg-Co-Y alloy.

Composition of the alloys are Mg-1at.% Co-2at.% Y and Mg-3.5at.% Co-8.5at. % Y and Mg-6at.% Co-8.5at.% Y. Master alloy ingot were prepared by casting, as-cast, annealed at 673K for 24h and 773K for 24h specimen were observed. TEM observation was performed by a conventional 200kV

microscope (JEM-2010HC) and STEM observations were performed by a conventional 200kV microscope (JEM-2010F) and an aberration-corrected 200kV microscope (JEM-ARM200F).

Experimental results show that 18R-LPSO structure is formed in Mg-Co-Y alloy. In addition, we find several novel LPSO structures, 15R, 12H and 21R. They are characterized by introducing intrinsic-1 type stacking fault periodically into 2H stacking, and Co/Y enrichment occurs at the three particular close-packed layers. We call these novel LPSO structures I_1 -LPSO and LPSO structures reported for Mg-TM-RE alloy I_2 -LPSO structure. We propose structural models of I_1 -LPSO structures in a Mg-Co-Y alloy.

P25

STRUCTURES OF NOVEL TYPE OF VACANCY-ORDERED $RE_{1-\delta}Ni_2$ LAVES COMPOUNDS

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$RE_{1-\delta}Ni_2$ (RE = Rare Earth) Laves compounds crystallize in C15-based vacancy-ordered superstructure in which vacancies substitute for RE atoms on particular site [1]. If these compounds have no vacancies, atomic radius ratio defined as r_{RE}/r_{Ni} (r_{RE} : RE atomic radius, r_{Ni} : Ni atomic radius) greatly exceeds ideal value of Laves, which is structurally instable. In contrast, structure with RE vacancies has lower radius ratio in nominal, hence is more favorable in terms of structural stability. The reason of formation of RE vacancies has been explained as above, however, there are still many unrevealed issues especially in its microstructure. In this study, we report novel type of vacancy-ordered superstructures discovered through TEM observation of $RE_{1-\delta}Ni_2$ (RE = Pr, Er) and discuss their relevancy to the structures which have already been reported. The nominal composition of the alloy used in this study is $RENi_2$ (RE = Pr, Er). Ingots were prepared by high frequency induction heating in an argon atmosphere. Solution treatment was carried out at 1148 K for $PrNi_2$ and 1318 K for $ErNi_2$ for 10h and cooled by water quenching. The microstructure of the alloy was investigated by TEM with a conventional microscope (JEM-2010HC).

The experimental results of the TEM observation showed the formation of novel type structures as well as conventional ones. $ErNi_2$ showed a vacancy-ordered structure with more enriched vacancies with higher symmetry than conventional one and $PrNi_2$ showed domain structure which consists of three variants

having another type of vacancy ordering. To investigate the stability of these phases, ab initio calculation was carried out to evaluate formation energy using VASP program. This result is to be discussed from the point of consistency against the experimental facts.

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P26

EFFECT OF SEVERE PLASTIC DEFORMATION ON THE PRECIPITATION BEHAVIOR OF α PHASE IN Ti5553 ALLOY

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Metastable β -Ti alloys are increasingly used as structural materials in aerospace industry thanks to their low density and good mechanical properties. The required mechanical properties depend on several strengthening mechanisms such as grain size, solid solution atoms and precipitation hardening, which all can be tuned during the various processing steps, leading to particular microstructures [N.clement, A. Lenain, P.J. Jacques, *JOM* 59 (2007) 50-53.]. Among these, the precipitation hardening, especially the precipitation of α phase during aging is very important to control the mechanical properties. A deep understanding of the phase transformation and the microstructural modification are thus required to allow the improvement of the mechanical properties. In the present research, the microstructure modification was carried out by severe plastic deformation (SPD) in the terms of high-pressure torsion (HPT) which could generate grain refinement and high density of lattice defects and subsequent aging in β -type Ti-5Al-5Mo-5V-3Cr (Ti5553) alloy.

The specimens were solution treated (ST) at 1000 °C which is above the β -transus temperature for 1 h followed by water quenching. Disks with a diameter of 10 mm and thickness of 0.85 mm were prepared for HPT processing. HPT processing was carried out under a pressure of 5 GPa and rotation speed of 0.2 rpm. Followed ST and HPT processing, isothermal aging was done at various temperatures ranging from 350 °C to 750 °C for 4 h followed by water quenching, respectively. The microstructures were investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

For solution treated Ti5553 alloy, acicular α phase precipitates with relatively coarse size was obtained upon isothermal aging. However, an ultrafine duplex ($\alpha+\beta$) microstructure composed of equiaxed α phase precipitates formed in HPT-processed Ti5553 alloy by aging. In addition, the composition analysis showed that the equiaxed α phase composed of higher content of Mo, V and Cr element.

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SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS USING GENERALIZED FINITE ELEMENT METHOD (GFEM)

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Shape sensitivity analysis is a structure design optimization [1] technique which has its roots in the variational formulation of continuum mechanics. Optimization problem comprise of computation of material derivatives, mutual potential energies and direct differentiation. Energy release rate i.e. J-integral the most suitable parameter to predict the failure/damage of structure is easy to compute, as it require only the multiplication of the displacement vector with sensitivity matrices. Mathematical formulation of this optimization problem manifest the dependency of sensitivity on displacement field and velocity field, responsible parameter to mimic the shape change of initial domain. By judiciously choosing the velocity field, the method only requires displacement response in a sub-domain close to the crack tip, thus making the method computationally efficient. The method thus requires an exact computation of displacement response in a sub-domain close to the crack tip. To this end in this study we have used a two scale GFEM for sensitivity analysis. GFEM is based on the enrichment of the classical finite element approximation.

The main objective of enrichment function is that it should able to reproduce the singular stress field near crack tip. Selection of enrichment function is done by a priori knowledge of solution. XFEM and mesh-less methods have used the partition of unity enrichment for solving the crack problems. Belytschko et al. [3] described methods based on the partition of unity for approximating discontinuous functions in finite element and mesh-less formulation. Enrichment function need not be known solely in closed framework but results from numerical simulation can be used as enrichment functions. Later authors used canonical domain containing features such as branched cracks, or closely spaced voids to generate what they called mesh-based handbook functions. This approach is very useful for the situations in which analytical expressions, which reflect the nature of solutions.

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P28

TEM/STEM OBSERVATIONS OF KINK-DEFORMED MICROSTRUCTURES IN LPSO-MG ALLOYS

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Recently, dilute magnesium alloys containing a few atomic percent of transition metals(TM) and rare-earth elements(RE) have attracted increasing attention for the excellent mechanical properties. These alloys consist of two phases; -Mg phase and synchronized long-period stacking ordered (LPSO) phase. When LPSO phase is compressed parallel to the basal plane, kink-deformation appears instead of twinning deformation which occurs in usual Mg alloys[1]. Therefore, kink-deformation is believed to play a key role for the realization of excellent mechanical properties of LPSO-based Mg alloys. Phenomenologically, kink deformation is understood as a result of pile-up of a large number of dislocations that have migrated on the limited (0001) plane for hcp crystals. However, there are few detailed observations of dislocation microstructures of kink- deformation bands. In this study, we investigate kink-deformed microstructures in the LPSO-Mg, focusing particularly on dislocation distributions around the kink-band.

LPSO-Mg alloys; hot-extruded Mg₉₇Zn₁Y₂ (at%) alloy with an extrusion ratio of 10:1, and rolled Mg₈₅Ni₆Y₉ alloy with 30% reduction. The two specimens were thinned by using mechanical polishing and ion milling. The microstructures were observed by a transmission electron microscopy (JEM-2010HC) and a scanning transmission electron microscopy (JEM-2010F).

For the Mg₉₇Zn₁Y₂ alloy and Mg₈₅Ni₆Y₉ alloy, 18R-type and 10H-type LPSO structures are formed, respectively. TEM observations confirmed that kink-deformation occurs for these two alloys. As a preliminary result, we find that significant dislocation structures are essentially formed around the kink bands in the present alloys. A number of *a*-dislocations are piled up and regularly arrayed along the *c*-axis to form a definite interface, across which the relevant crystal is sharply bended with an angle of 1~2 degree. Arrays of *c*- dislocations are also frequently observed, which seem to prevent crack initiations caused by the crystal bend. Microstructural similarity between the kink-deformed LPSO-Mg and hcp-Mg crystals may indicate that the kink bands in both specimens are formed by the similar deformation mechanism. Further details of the dislocation features will be systematically described from an atomic-scale to micrometer-scale, focusing on the elemental dislocation core structures and their macroscopic configurations.

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P29

PHOTOLITHOGRAPHY OF PARYLENE-C/TA₂O₅ HYBRID GATE INSULATOR FOR FUTURE MOTT TRANSISTORS

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The conventional semiconductor device fabrication technology is facing an impending problem called “miniaturization limit”. To overcome this problem, alternative technologies are being explored. One of the most promising and seemingly a unique solution among those, is to adopt the so-called Mott insulator (e.g., κ -(BEDT-TTF)₂Cu[N(CN)₂]Br, V₂O₃, NiX₂, and AM₄X₈; A \equiv Ga or Ge, M \equiv V, Nb, or Ge, X \equiv S or Se) as the channel materials of field effect transistor (FET). The Mott insulator shows metal-insulator transition (Mott transition) and the number of carriers in the channel changes quite drastically from zero to a huge number. Several groups have reported electric field-driven Mott transitions using an electric double layer (EDL) of electrolyte for a gate insulator [1]. EDL transistor is not viable as an application, due to liquid nature of the electrolyte. Recently, Eyvazov *et al.* have developed a novel solid-state Parylene-C/Ta₂O₅ hybrid gate insulator and achieved a *continuous control* of the sheet charge density up to 10¹³ cm⁻², while *keeping the quality of the interface* between the channel material and the gate-insulator almost ideal [2]. In the present work we use this Parylene-C/Ta₂O₅ hybrid gate insulator and try to fabricate μ m-scale FET devices by using photolithography.

The FET devices are fabricated on an atomically flat SrTiO₃ (STO) single-crystalline substrate. STO is not a Mott insulator but has characteristics similar to many Mott insulators. It has a perovskite structure and becomes metallic upon electron doping. In addition the STO substrate with atomically flat surface is easily available from vendors and is a widely used substrate for thin film deposition of Mott insulators. Therefore, we believe that once a method of fabricating FET with Parylene-C/Ta₂O₅ hybrid gate insulator on the STO substrate is established, it can be then utilized to fabricate the real Mott FET.

The source and drain electrode pattern is made using a conventional photolithography method. However, since Mott insulators are quite ionic, due to the nature of the electron localization, a chemical treatment during photolithography can create a large number of ionic defects on its surface. These defects can drastically affect both the carrier number as well as the carrier mobility. Hence, to protect the surface of the channel, a 5 nm Parylene-C layer is coated on it before the lithography. The electrodes are fabricated using rf-sputtering of Al metal. However, to facilitate the ohmic contact of the electrodes with the STO, the Parylene film is etched selectively using UV radiations in an Ozone environment, before the deposition of Al. But the electrodes fabricated using this method have burrs at their edges. These burrs pose a significant problem as they can cause an electrical breakdown. To avoid these burrs, we made an undercut

structure on the photoresist. Size of this undercut structure is controlled to obtain the best shape of the metal electrodes.

Ta₂O₅ is a widely known high-k oxide with a dielectric constant of about 25. But a direct deposition of Ta₂O₅ on the ionic Mott insulator results in a huge number of defects on the surface. By the Parylene coating, this unfavorable damage to the surface is also avoided.

In addition to the basic problems, we are going to discuss other *ad-hoc* problems of the lithography of the Parylene-C/Ta₂O₅ hybrid insulator, and possibly a FET characteristics of STO controlled by the hybrid gate insulator.

An optimization of the photolithography process of FET on STO with Parylene-C/Ta₂O₅ hybrid gate insulator will be reported. This is an important step in fabricating a more realistic Mott transistor and to create a path for future realization of Mottronics.

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P30

A NOVEL APPROACH FOR MODELING SPATIAL VARIABILITY OF PHYTOPLANKTON IN OCEAN ECOSYSTEM

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The measurement of phytoplankton distributions in ocean ecosystems provides the basis for the elucidation of the influences of physical process on plankton dynamics. Technological advances allow for the measurement of phytoplankton data to greater resolution. High-resolution data displays high spatial variability.

In conventional mathematical models, the mean value of the measured variable is approximated in order to compare with the model output, which may misinterpret the actual scenario of planktonic ecosystems, especially when looking at micro-scale level. To consider intermittency of variables, in this work, a new modeling approach to the planktonic ecosystem is applied, called the closure approach which has been widely used in Physical Ocean modeling. Using this approach for a simple nutrient-phytoplankton

model, in this theoretical study, we have shown how consideration of the fluctuating part of a model variable can affect the system dynamics. Also we have found a critical value of variance of overall fluctuating terms below which the conventional non-closure model and the mean value from the closure model exhibit the same result. Therefore, this analysis gives an impression about the importance of the fluctuating part of model variables and also an idea when to use closure approach for model formulation. Comparisons of plot of mean versus standard deviation of phytoplankton at different depths as obtained using this new modeling approach with real observations give good conformity to this approach.

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CUBIC QUASICRYSTAL IN A RAPIDLY-SOLIDIFIED Mg-Al ALLOY

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It is commonly accepted that the definition of quasicrystal should include a rotational symmetry forbidden in periodic crystals. On the other hand, the quasicrystal with a crystallographic point group is possibly argued both theoretically and experimentally [1,2]. In a rapidly-solidified Mg-Al alloy, intriguing electron diffraction patterns (EDPs) were reported, which show a cubic symmetry with aperiodic arrays of Bragg reflections that appears in relation with the irrational number $\sqrt{3}$ [2]. In the present work, we investigate the detailed structure of the rapidly-solidified Mg-Al phase based on direct structure observations using STEM.

In the Mg-Al system there exists β -Mg₂Al₃ phase in the vicinity of the composition Mg-61 at.% Al, which consist of icosahedral and tetrahedral close packing. In a rapidly-solidified Mg-61 at.% Al alloy, 2-fold, 3-fold, and 4-fold EDPs are obtained, which shows that the structure has the cubic point group. However, the relevant diffraction spots are arranged aperiodically. Especially in the 2-fold EDP, a high density of the spots is observed, and the corresponding HADDF-STEM image shows several remarkable features. Two length scales, L and S, can be definitely observed, and they are arranged quasiperiodically along the 3-fold axis. Both the number ratio and length ratio of L and S are estimated to be around 1.38, and their arrangement can be well described by the hyperspace crystallography. Namely, a physical space tilted by the angle θ , where $\tan\theta \approx 1.38$, with respect to the 2-dimensional square lattice successfully generates the observed quasiperiodic pattern. We construct a simple model without detailed atomic decoration, and the simulated EDPs of the model reproduces fairly well the experimental patterns. Further analysis of the images reveals that the present quasiperiodic structure has similar local structure to the β -Mg₂Al₃ phase; two lengths correspond to L and S may be reasonably defined.

The quasicrystal with a cubic symmetry is unambiguously determined for the first time, based on a direct structural observation. The present results strongly suggest that the noncrystallographic rotational

symmetry is not an essential factor to form the quasiperiodic structure, raising a very fundamental, universal question on the physical origin of a long-range order of condensed matters.

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P32

CATALYTIC ACTIVITY OF ACID- AND/OR ALKALI-TREATED Ni₃(Al,V) ATOMIZED POWDER FOR CH₃OH DECOMPOSITION

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Ni-base intermetallic compounds have potential as a catalyst for hydrogen production reactions. For example, Ni₃Al exhibited reasonable catalytic activity and high selectivity for CH₃OH decomposition [1]. The catalytic activity was improved after dipping in an alkali solution, in which Al was selectively dissolved and made fine Ni particles on the surface.

In this study, we for the first time examined the catalytic properties of a two-phase intermetallic compound Ni₃Al/Ni₃V with a eutectic lamella structure. V as well as Al is electrochemically more active than Ni and we thus expected that the selective dissolution occurs in the alkali treatment and improves the catalytic activity.

Powders of 75Ni-5Al-20V (at%) with diameters ranging from 25 to 50 micron meters were prepared by a gas-atomize method, and then were annealed at 1173 K to form the eutectic lamella structure. The alkali treatment was carried out in a 20 wt% Na₂CO₃ solution or a NaOH solution at 373 K for 24 h. Before the alkali treatment, the powders were dipped in a 3 vol.% HCl solution at 298 K for 6 h, expecting an increase in the specific surface area. The catalytic activity was isochronally measured from 513 to 793 K and the methanol conversion was analyzed.

The X-ray diffraction analysis proved the existence of the Ni₃V phase in the annealed powders, but it was difficult to clearly assign the Ni₃Al phase due to the overlap of the peaks from both phases and its low volume fraction.

The annealed powders showed some catalytic activity for methanol decomposition above 713K, and the activity increased with temperature. Note that the catalyst activity was significantly improved by the acid and alkali treatment, as follows. Firstly, the acid treatment slightly shifted the conversion vs. temperature curve about 10 K lower from that of the annealed powder. Secondly, the subsequent alkali

treatment improved the activity more: the conversion curve further shifted 60 K lower from that of the acid-treated powders. The effect of the alkali treatment was identical for both Na₂CO₃- and NaOH-solutions.

The Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) analysis showed that the specific surface area increased after the acid treatment, which should yield the slight improvement of the catalytic activity. It is noted that according to the inductively coupled plasma (ICP) analysis of the solutions, Ni, Al, and V were dissolved in the acid treatment. We thus assume that the surface kept its chemical composition through the acid treatment

In the alkali treatments, no Ni but V and/or Al were dissolved: only V in the Na₂CO₃ solution and V and Al in the NaOH solution. The selective dissolution suggested that Ni was enriched on the surface by these alkali treatments. In addition, we confirmed that the BET surface area significantly increased. These surface changes should be responsible for the significant increase of the catalytic activity. In the poster presentation, we will give the excellent effect of the combination of the two alkali treatments.

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P33

DEFORMATION RESPONSE OF PURE MAGNESIUM UNDER DYNAMIC COMPRESSION LOADING

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Nowadays, weight reduction of automotive is required for improving the fuel consumption and reducing the greenhouse gas. Application of Mg alloys is one of the possible ways because of their low densities, although they exhibit limited ductility at the ambient temperature. To be used for the structural components in the vehicles, the material should exhibit sufficient ductility and/or toughness not only at static but also at dynamic strain rates, since the components are often fractured by shear force under dynamic loading against foreign object damage.

In the present study, the deformation behavior of pure magnesium was examined at a high strain rate of $1.4 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, corresponding to the crashing speed of the vehicles, by using a split Hopkinson pressure bar (SHPB). Deformed macrostructure was inspected by SEM/EBSD to clarify the deformation mechanism under the dynamic compression. Stress-strain curves exhibited a typical concave shape suggesting the formation of $\{10\bar{1}2\}$ deformation twins in the whole grains at both the high strain rate and a quasi-static strain rate, while yield stress increased by decreasing the average grain size from 125 to 6 micrometers. Inspection of the deformed microstructure by SEM/EBSD revealed that the fraction of

the {10 $\bar{1}$ 2} deformation twin increased at the high strain rate although the average thickness of the twin was reduced at a fixed strain. Therefore, it was worthy noted that the interaction between generated dislocations and deformation twins was enhanced, since the strain hardening rate of the stress-strain relation increased with strain rate. The rapid increase in the hardening rate caused the stress concentration and resulted in decreasing the compressive strain under the dynamic loading.

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CHIRALITY INDUCTION BY *E-Z* PHOTOISOMERIZATION IN [2,2]PARACYCLOPHANE-BRIDGED AZOBENZENE DIMER

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Introduction of asymmetry in molecular systems by physical means has been enormously discussed in the last few decades to understand inherent reason behind homo-chirality in nature. Enantio-differentiating photoisomerization of the molecular systems with dynamic asymmetry by circular polarized light is one of such candidates [1]. Our recent interest was to propose a novel concept for the introduction of chirality in an achiral system by exploiting photochromism of azobenzene. In 2011 we succeeded in the generation and optical resolution of point chirality in an achiral precursor [2]. Here we extended our concept into planar chiral system utilizing substituted [2.2]paracyclophane as chiral moiety [3]. On suitable wavelength light irradiation, *E-Z* isomerization of one of the azobenzene moieties attached to [2.2]paracyclophane turned to generate an asymmetry in the structure and on refluxing; *Z-E* thermal isomerization regenerated the initial achiral molecule. This ON-OFF switching of chirality was repeatedly accomplished by light and reflux, respectively, which was confirmed by HPLC and CD spectroscopic methods.

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P35

BAND GAP ENGINEERING OF TITANIUM DIOXIDE NANOCRYSTALS BY BACTERIAL RESPIRATION

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A simple biogenic route to narrow the band gap of TiO₂ nanocrystals for visible light application has been proposed. When an electrochemically active biofilm was challenged with a solution of Degussa-TiO₂ using sodium acetate as electron donor, grayish blue-colored TiO₂ nanocrystals were obtained via bacterial respiration. Band gap study showed that band gap of the modified TiO₂ nanocrystals was significantly reduced compared to the unmodified white Degussa TiO₂. The proposed protocol appears to be an efficient protocol for engineering the band gap of semiconductor nanocrystals and the electrochemically active biofilm seems to act as a ‘band gap engineer’.

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